

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OFURUNE****FIRST NAME: HENRY****PROGRAM CODE: DSSD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This essay discusses the ACA-401D period one coursepack on the basics of essay writing. While writing is not new to me, Turabian style is new. So, I will discuss the basics of writing such as the building blocks of a good academic paper. Next, I will cover how to research for relevant information for an academic essay. In the process, I will give details on nitty-gritty including drafting the first essay and the structure of the essay. Thereafter, this writeup discusses plagiarism and how to avoid it. I will touch on writing style particularly the Turabian style and the choice of American English over British English in academic writing. Lastly, I will discuss the Chicago Manual Style and its impact on writing style. This paper ends with an appropriate conclusion on my overview of the ACA-401D coursepack and my expectations of its impact on my doctoral journey.

2) ESSAY WRITING: THE BASICS

Like everything we do in life that has a purpose, academic writing has the aim of using evidence to persuade its readers on a topic (EUCLID 2019, 6). In the process of providing evidence, EUCLID mentioned that a good academic essay has a thesis statement that answers a question (ibid.). I should use credible academic references to provide evidence on my viewpoint on the topic. The research will assist the academic writer to provide, for example, information, academic text, and evidence to back the topic (ibid.). An academic essay includes generally three sections namely, introduction, the body of the essay, and a conclusion. The academic essay must include references or bibliography for my readers to confirm my sources (ibid.).

A critical aspect of academic essay writing is research because as EUCLID notes research provides evidence and facts that are used to develop an argument and a thesis in answering the essay question (EUCLID 2019, 7). That means that for instance, as an academic writer, one should consult many sources in the library and suggested readings using the catalogue to search for subject searches before writing the essay (ibid.). I should start early with research to have ample time to develop the topic (ibid.). Also, EUCLID emphasized that using notes during research allows the researcher to build a base for the essay (ibid.). The notes will assist in organizing ideas, deciding what points I want to discuss, and in what order I will do so (ibid.).

In drafting the essay, I should use the notes I made for the first essay. A draft is important because it assists the writer to decide how the question would be answered, evidence and examples to use. I will use the draft to structure the argument in the essay (EUCLID 2019, 8). The structure of the essay starts with an introduction that EUCLID described as a short orientation on the topic. An introduction is a broad sentence that summarizes an essay (ibid.). It also serves a roadmap or what the essay contains (ibid.).

The body of the essay follows the introduction. According to EUCLID, I will use this section to discuss the answer to the thesis question using evidence and examples to prove my knowledge of the material (ibid.). The body uses paragraphs to expatiate on the topic. Each paragraph should begin with a topic sentence that gives the main idea of the paragraph (ibid.). The lead sentence is followed by a supporting sentence that develops the point with evidence for research on the subject (ibid.). One pitfall that I found is that of leaving the evidence hanging. That is if I give the evidence without analysing and interpreting the evidence (ibid.). To avoid this pitfall, EUCLID emphasized that I should comment on the evidence by stating the significance and implication of the evidence (ibid.).

The structure of an essay ends with a conclusion (ibid.). To write a conclusion I will begin with a broad statement that summarizes the main point and show possible implications and future research that can be done on the topic (ibid.).

3) PLAGIARISM

As an academic writer, I should be wary of plagiarism in the course of writing an academic essay. According to EUCLID, plagiarism is when a writer uses the information without acknowledging the author (EUCLID 2019, 10). For example, if I quote, copy, and paste the information in an essay and did not reference the author that is plagiarism (ibid.). In academics, plagiarism is unethical and a serious offense with grave consequences (ibid.). Hence, I must give credit to the source of information such as data, quotes, and visuals used in an essay. Therefore, I can use quotations and paraphrases to cite a source.

4) IMPORTANCE OF USING STYLE GUIDE

Despite the basic rules of academic writing, it is interesting to me to note that academic essays differ in style such as a Turabian style which I used to write this essay (EUCLID 2019, 29). Styles of writing go beyond grammar, punctuation, and vocabulary to include the type of font used, preferred length of sentences, and the layout of the manuscript (ibid.). EUCLID also stated that writing styles define the voice preference whether active or passive voice. The writing style is also detailed to the extent of specifying paragraph numbering, indentation, and use of English spelling (EUCLID 2019, 30).

5) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

The influence of the use of American or British English in academic writing is based on the population of the country, rate of higher education, the appeal of the culture to people, the political and economic position of the country amongst other factors (EUCLID 2019, 32). No wonder that the American English dominates academic writing because of its higher indices in factors listed (EUCLID 2019, 29). The difference between the American and British English include spelling, punctuation, pronunciation, the different or additional meaning of words (EUCLID 2019, 33). Examples of the same pronunciation of words but different spelling are Plough and Plow, Colour, and Color. I also note instances of the same concept but different expressions in the English language such as Petrol and gasoline, Barrister and solicitor.

6) CHICAGO MANUAL STYLE (CMS)

Chicago Style is a style used to format research papers and books (EUCLID 2019, 49). Chicago Manual Style (CMS) Crib Sheet is a family of a style guide that is used in academic writing (ibid.). CMS Crib Sheet stipulates the use of abbreviations, compound words, numbers, dates, quotations, headings, footnotes, etc (ibid.).

The Chicago Manual Style recommends using the latest *Webster's Third New International Dictionary and Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary* for spelling. I was surprised to know that if more than a form a word is listed the first form should be used. Also, if there is a difference between *Webster's Third New International Dictionary and Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary* the Collegiate Dictionary should be used because it represents the latest lexical research of the two dictionaries (ibid.).

Abbreviations are used in figure captions, tables, notes, and references, and rarely in a text (ibid.). I observed that the general guideline for abbreviation is that it can only be used when its context is clear to the reader (ibid.). When an acronym is used, it must first be introduced by writing the complete word and putting the acronym in parentheses or the other way round (ibid.).

Capitalization is in 3 forms namely; full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps. In the full caps, for instance, every character in the word is capitalized (EUCLID 2019, 50). In heading caps, all the words in the title are capitalized including the conjunctions, adjectives, nouns, and pronouns. On the other hand, only the first word of the title and the first word after a colon and proper nouns (ibid.).

7) CONCLUSION

This course material is an eye-opener to me. The ACA-401D period one-course material will assist in building my academic writing skills throughout my doctorate. The course provides a good foundation to shape my writing in Turabian style. I gained new knowledge for instance; I learned the form of a word to choose in a dictionary if there are more than a form. I realized that it was practical for plagiarism to be a serious academic offense. I think that the arrangement of headings and indentation of paragraphs will require more practice to get used to. However, I am confident that as I advance in my study my ability to use the Turabian style will get better.

REFERENCE

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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